

Curvature and Wavelength – 8 Theory

O Manor

June 20, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the framework and intersecting it with the equation of wavelength and energy, the author will attempt at constructing and reasoning an analogous version. The version will be presented within varying Lorentz manifolds with (3,1) signature. These are invoked stationary by EL operator.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\varpi = \frac{2\pi}{t_0} = ck \quad (1.1)$$

$$k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \rightarrow \lambda = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (1.11)$$

What is the analogue for the frequency in a varying manifold such as a Lorentz manifold? One will start with the wavelength. In the 8T framework wavelength would be 2π divided by the distance between positive summations. That is two net curvatures such as the photon, associated with $N_V = (+5)$, we only adjust the denominator. The more dense curvature summations we have in a unit circle, the shorter the wavelength as the photon is associated with a positive net curvature on the manifold. that is precisely how the coupling series was derived.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.12)$$

The glowing blue as two emphasize the short wavelength and the high energy due to large curvature summation per unit circle. The opposite would be obvious, insignificant amount of curvature summation would be synonymous with glowing red. The point to be taken is that the wave number can be replaced with the measure of curvature. In particular, summation of photons per unit matrix is analogues with equation (1.12). if one constructed properly:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{k} \rightarrow \frac{\int_{L1}^{L2} s(ds)}{\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i} \quad (1.13)$$

That is the manifold varying length divided by net curvature summation, which are the photons on the manifold, would be our measure of wavelength. Since its quite complicated to do the integral in such framework, we can simplify and adjust only the denominator.

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i} \quad (1.14)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)